

A Study on the Branching Patterns of the Middle Cerebral Artery and Its Clinical Implications

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Abstract:

The middle cerebral artery (MCA) plays a crucial role in the cerebral vascular system, supplying blood to regions associated with motor, sensory, and language functions. Variability in its branching pattern poses important implications for neurovascular interventions and clinical diagnostics. This cross-sectional study investigates MCA branching patterns, focusing on bifurcation, trifurcation, and other rare configurations to understand their prevalence and significance in neurosurgical planning and stroke management. Data were collected from both cadaveric samples and patient imaging, allowing for a thorough analysis of morphological variations. Findings reveal bifurcation as the predominant pattern, followed by trifurcation, with limited demographic influences observed on pattern distribution. These results highlight the necessity for customized clinical approaches in neurovascular procedures, advancing patient care and enhancing neurosurgical outcomes.

Keywords: Middle cerebral artery, branching patterns, bifurcation, trifurcation, neurosurgery, stroke management and anatomical variations.

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Introduction

The middle cerebral artery (MCA) is a major vessel in the cerebrovascular system, crucial for supplying blood to regions of the brain associated with essential functions such as motor control, sensory processing, and language comprehension. Emerging from the internal carotid artery, the MCA divides into several branches, each supplying specific cortical areas. Consequently, the MCA's branching pattern is of considerable interest in clinical neuroscience, as its configuration influences both the approach and outcome of various neurosurgical procedures, including those for stroke management, aneurysm intervention, and tumor resections [1,2]. Among the branching patterns of the MCA, bifurcation is the most commonly observed, where the artery divides into two primary branches, designated as the superior and inferior trunks [3,4]. Other configurations, such as trifurcation, where the MCA divides into three branches, or more complex arrangements, though less frequent, present notable considerations for neurosurgeons. These anatomical variations can impact surgical procedures and increase the risk of intraoperative complications if not adequately understood. Variability in the MCA branching pattern has also been implicated in the occurrence and severity of cerebral infarctions, particularly

when specific branches supply areas vulnerable to ischemic events [5]. Anatomical studies have documented different MCA branching configurations across populations, indicating that while some variations are universally common, others may be influenced by genetic or demographic factors. For instance, previous research suggests that bifurcation is a globally common pattern, with studies conducted in both Eastern and Western populations confirming its prevalence. However, the incidence of trifurcation and other rare patterns appears to vary, underscoring the need for further investigation to confirm these trends and their clinical implications [6,7]. This study focuses on the MCA branching pattern in a diverse population, analyzing cadaveric and clinical imaging data to establish the prevalence of bifurcation, trifurcation, and other configurations. By understanding these variations, the study aims to enhance surgical planning, reduce intraoperative risks, and inform diagnostic strategies, particularly in the context of stroke management and neurosurgery. The findings have the potential to contribute significantly to the anatomical knowledge base and support clinical decision-making by providing insights into the vascular architecture of the MCA.

Aim and Objectives

Aim: To analyze the branching pattern of the middle cerebral artery and its implications for neurosurgical interventions and cerebrovascular diagnostics.

Objectives:

- To document and classify the MCA branching patterns observed in a cross-sectional sample.
- To evaluate the potential clinical implications of these variations for neurovascular procedures.

Material and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Anatomy in a tertiary care hospital, utilizing cadaveric dissection and clinical imaging to analyze MCA branching patterns. The study population comprised individuals aged 18 years and older, representing a range of demographic backgrounds.

Cadaveric samples were obtained from the anatomy department, and imaging data from patients

undergoing cerebral angiography were included for a comprehensive analysis. Ethical clearance was obtained, and all data were anonymized prior to analysis.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Individuals aged 18 and older.
- Patients undergoing cerebral angiography.
- Cadaveric specimens with an intact MCA.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Cases with significant MCA pathology affecting branching patterns.
- Patients with a history of major cerebrovascular surgery.

Data analysis involved categorizing branching patterns into bifurcation, trifurcation, and other complex configurations. Frequencies of each pattern were calculated, and statistical comparisons were performed to assess the influence of age, sex, and other demographic factors on branching patterns.

Results

Table 1: Distribution of MCA Branching Patterns

Pattern	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Bifurcation	60	48
Trifurcation	40	32
Complex	20	20

Table 1 illustrates the distribution of MCA branching patterns, showing bifurcation as the most common configuration, followed by trifurcation and complex patterns.

Table 2: Demographic Influence on MCA Branching Patterns

Demographic Factor	Bifurcation (%)	Trifurcation (%)	Complex (%)
Age < 40	40	30	10
Age ≥ 40	60	35	10
Male	50	30	15
Female	48	32	20

Table 2 presents the distribution of MCA branching patterns according to age and sex, with no statistically significant demographic influence observed on branching configurations.

Discussion

The results of this study underscore the variability of MCA branching patterns, with bifurcation emerging as the predominant configuration. This finding aligns with previous studies in multiple populations, which report bifurcation as the most frequent branching type observed in the MCA. For instance, a study by Chen et al. (2019) documented a similar distribution in an East Asian population, with bifurcation present in over 50% of cases [8].

These findings reinforce the notion that bifurcation is a universal pattern, perhaps due to underlying genetic or developmental factors influencing MCA formation [9,10]. The clinical relevance of

identifying these branching patterns cannot be overstated. Bifurcation, trifurcation, and complex branching configurations pose distinct challenges during neurovascular interventions. Studies by Bender et al. (2018) have highlighted the implications of bifurcation patterns in endovascular procedures, as these configurations necessitate a higher degree of precision to avoid collateral damage to adjacent brain regions [11].

Furthermore, trifurcation patterns have been associated with increased procedural complexity, requiring tailored surgical approaches to mitigate risks of ischemia or vessel rupture [12]. Although no significant demographic factors influenced MCA branching in this study, understanding these patterns remains essential for comprehensive neurovascular education. Variability in MCA anatomy can influence outcomes in cases of ischemic stroke, aneurysmal clipping, and tumor

resections. Neurosurgeons must be cognizant of such anatomical variations, as MCA branching directly affects the planning and execution of delicate procedures.

The anatomical diversity observed in MCA patterns across populations emphasizes the need for further research, particularly in high-risk groups such as elderly individuals and those with a family history of cerebrovascular diseases [13,14].

In sum, the present study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of MCA anatomy, serving as a reference for clinicians in neurosurgery and neurology. It underscores the importance of personalized care approaches, particularly in complex neurosurgical procedures where anatomical variability is a significant determinant of success.

Conclusion

This study highlights the prevalence and clinical implications of various MCA branching patterns, establishing bifurcation as the most common configuration among a diverse cohort.

Although demographic factors showed limited influence on branching patterns, the anatomical variations documented herein are of significant clinical relevance, particularly for neurosurgeons and interventional radiologists. Understanding MCA anatomy and its branching patterns enhances surgical planning, supports more precise diagnostic imaging interpretations, and reduces the risk of intraoperative complications.

By documenting these variations, this study contributes a valuable reference for neurovascular procedures, ultimately improving patient outcomes through better-informed and individualized approaches.

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